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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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THE POWERS OF THE CENTRAL BANK OF NIGERIA ON CURRENCY REDESIGN: THE EXTENT OF COMPLIANCE WITH LAW IN THE 2023 NAIRA REDESIGN POLICY

By

Ibrahim Danjuma*

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ABSTRACT

Countries around the world redesign and reissue their legal tender for several reasons. The prevention of counterfeit currency is a key motivation. A country's ability to limit counterfeiting to a minimum and remain ahead of counterfeiting threats is made possible by redesigning its national currency. According to best practice, the issuance of new currency should be undertaken every five to eight years. Usually, the issuance of legal tender of any economy is the duty of the apex bank. In Nigeria the central bank of Nigeria (CBN) Act of 2007, as amended vests in the bank the responsibility to issue and manage the country's legal tender currency. This paper examines the legal framework and authority of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) on currency redesign in Nigeria. In order to ensure that this study achieves its aims and objectives, the methodology used involves doctrinal source of legal provisions relating to the Central Bank of Nigeria Act 2007 and other relevant laws. The research finding reveals that the Central Bank of Nigeria has a wide range of powers and responsibilities on currency redesign under the CBN Act of 2007, but it also faces some challenges and limitations in exercising them effectively. It recommends that the CBN should enhance its public engagement and transparency on currency redesign issues and adopt a more proactive and innovative approach to currency management and control.

Keywords: *Currency, Currency Redesign, Power, Central Bank of Nigeria.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) is the only principal banking institution in Nigeria saddled with the task of issuing of currency as legal tender in Nigeria by virtue of Section 2 (b) of the Central Bank of Nigeria Act, 2007. Attached to with this responsibility, the CBN Act has vested the redesign of currency on the Central Bank of Nigeria.

In the exercise of such function, the CBN has on numerous instances redesigned Nigeria legal tender. This includes the July 1962 redesign when Nigeria's currency was changed from bearing "the Federation of Nigeria" to the "Federal Republic of Nigeria". In 2007 and 2009, CBN as part of economic reforms in the country redesigned the 50 naira, 20 naira, 10 naira and 5 naira in to a polymer substrate while the 1 naira and the 50 kobo were re-issued in a new design.¹

Amidst high inflation, fuel scarcity and strained economy, the CBN recently undertook a redesign of the country's national currency, the Naira. The primary goal of this redesign was to combat counterfeiting and enhance the security features of the currency. The CBN's Naira redesign has garnered widespread interest, as it is a significant change for the country's monetary system. Therefore, this study provides an examination of the extent and procedure of the CBN's power on naira redesign in order to determine whether or not there was compliance with relevant laws with emphasis on the following.

1. What are the legal and regulatory frameworks governing the currency redesign process in Nigeria?
2. What are the specific powers granted to the Central Bank of Nigeria under the Central Bank of Nigeria Act, 2007, concerning currency redesign?
3. How does the Central Bank of Nigeria exercise these powers in practice, particularly in the process of currency issuance, withdrawal, and demonetization?

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¹The Guardian (2022). The History of currency introduction and redesign in Nigeria. The Guardian Nigeria News - Nigeria and World News. <https://guardian.ng/opinion/the-history-of-currency-introduction-and-redesign-in-nigeria/>

In accomplishing these tasks, the paper begins with the history and evolution of the CBN Act; examines the powers and functions of CBN; Currency redesign; discusses the history of currency redesign in Nigeria; identifies the importance and rationale for the currency redesign; identifies the statutory authority on naira redesign; discusses the decision-making process and approval mechanisms for naira redesign; ascertains the relevant agencies needed to be collaborated for the purpose of naira redesign; examines the guidelines for currency design and redesign; discusses compliance and enforcement mechanisms, reporting and accountability requirements; examines the currency redesign by the CBN in 2023 thereby identifying the extent of compliance and the surrounding controversies. Lastly, the paper identifies the findings in the conclusion, and offers recommendation on how to address issues identified.

2. HISTORICAL BACKGROUND AND EVOLUTION OF THE CBN ACT

The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) was established by the 1958 Act of Parliament, which was based on an inquiry into the banking practices in Nigeria at the time.² The Central Bank of Nigeria Act has been amended several times since then, in 1991, 1993, 1997, 1998, 1999 and 2007,³ to reflect the changing needs and challenges of the Nigerian economy.

The CBN Act of 2007, which is the current version, charges the CBN with the overall control and administration of the monetary and financial sector policies of the Federal Government.⁴ Some of the functions and roles of the CBN under this Act are:

- 1 Implementing monetary policies in Nigeria such as regulating the currency, credit and exchange rate, to ensure price stability, high employment and economic growth.
- 2 Setting the official interest rates for all the commercial banks in Nigeria, to control inflation and the exchange rate.
- 3 Issuing legal tender currency (the naira) in Nigeria, and managing its supply and circulation.

² Functions of the CBN and Brief History – <https://nigerianfinder.com/functions-of-the-cbn/>. Accessed on 12th September 2023

³ Central Bank of Nigeria | About CBN. <https://www.cbn.gov.ng/AboutCBN/>. Accessed on 12th September 2023

⁴ *ibid*

- 4 Serving as a banker to the Federal Government of Nigeria, and managing its debt and fiscal operations.
- 5 Serving as a banker to other banks in Nigeria, and providing them with liquidity support and supervision.
- 6 Acting as a lender of last resort to banks and other financial institutions in case of financial distress.
- 7 Promoting financial inclusion, stability and development in Nigeria, by supporting microfinance, agricultural credit, mobile banking and other initiatives.

The evolution of the Act in Nigeria reflects the dynamic nature of the Nigerian economy and its integration with the global financial system. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has faced various challenges and opportunities over the years, such as the Structural Adjustment Program (SAP) in 1986 which introduced some deregulation and liberalization measures; the removal and restoration of its autonomy in 1997 and 1998 respectively; the introduction of new currencies and denominations in 1973, 1984 and 2007; the consolidation of banks in 2005; the global financial crisis in 2008; and the recent recession and recovery in 2016 and 2017. The CBN has also been involved in various initiatives and reforms to improve its performance and governance, such as the Vision 2020, the Financial System Strategy (FSS) 2020, the Code of Corporate Governance for Banks, and the Asset Management Corporation of Nigeria (AMCON).⁵

3. OVERVIEW OF THE CENTRAL BANK'S POWERS AND FUNCTIONS

The Central Bank of Nigeria came into existence in 1959 consequent upon the Central Bank of Nigeria Ordinance 1958 (as amended in 1991, 1993, 1997, 1998, 1999 and 2007), with an initial capital of three million Naira. This has been increased to one hundred billion Naira by the CBN Act 2007, to reflect the recent wave of capitalization imposed by the Central Bank of Nigeria itself on all Banks and other financial

⁵ Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN): Purpose, functions, power & history. <https://www.makemoney.ng/central-bank-of-nigeria/>. Accessed on 12th September 2023

institutions in Nigeria. The Bank was established out of the sheer need to maintain safety, soundness and stability in the banking sector. This was due to the series of lapses and inadequacies in the Banking Ordinance 1952 which was regulatory organ in the sector then. The operational Act of the Bank-1991 was repealed by the 2007 Act, guaranteeing for the first time the Bank's independence.

3.1 Powers of the Central Bank of Nigeria

i. Power to grant banking license: Any intending entrepreneur who desires to form a banking business alone or jointly with others in Nigeria shall apply in writing to the Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria for the grant of license to start operation.⁶ The application shall contain the following:

- a. Feasibility report of the proposed bank;
- b. A draft copy of the Memorandum and Articles of Association of the proposed bank;
- c. A list of directors, shareholders and principal officers of the bank and their particulars;
- d. The prescribed application fees; and
- e. Such other information, documents and reports as the Central Bank may, from time to time, specify.⁷

It is pertinent to note that after the requirement of Section 3 of the 2007 Act is met, the Act requires the shareholders of the proposed bank to deposit a minimum paid-up share capital in case of liquidation for commercial banks² which now stands at 25 Billion Naira instead of the 2 Billion Naira hitherto being deposited with the Central Bank of Nigeria and insured by the Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation in accordance with Section 2 (1) (a) of the 2006 Act. This policy was put in place to reposition the Central Bank of Nigeria and the Nigerian financial system to meet the 21st Century challenges and in the quest of pursuing the core mandate of the Central Bank of Nigeria that is the promotion of a sound financial system in Nigeria.⁸ The Central Bank of Nigeria policy of 2004 brought about the issues of mergers and

⁶ Section 3 (1) of the BOFIA, 2020.

⁷ Section 3 (1) (a-e) of the BOFIA,2020

⁸ Section 1 (2) (d) of the CBN, Act 2 020

acquisitions in the banking industry.⁹ It is important to note that where the proposed bank has complied with the requirement of Section 3 (2) of the 2007 Act by depositing 25 Billion Naira with the Central Bank of Nigeria, the Governor of the Central Bank may proceed to issue a license to the proposed bank with or without conditions or refused to issue same¹⁰, since issuance of a license is discretionary. Where he refused to issue license, he need not give any reason for the refusal¹¹ but he will re-pay or release the minimum paid-up share capital deposited with the Central Bank of Nigeria to the applicant as part of the pre-qualification requirements for the grant of license notwithstanding the money is invested or not. Where it is invested, the investment income be paid by the Central Bank of Nigeria after administrative expenses and income tax has been deducted.¹² And where the application for license is granted, the Central Bank shall give written notice to the applicant who is to pay the fees for the license.¹³

ii. Power to revoke license granted bank or vary the conditions stipulated in a license: The Governor of the Central Bank has the power to revoke a license granted to a licensed bank under the 2007 Act or vary the conditions stipulated in the license from time to time. Where the Central Bank of Nigeria revoked a license granted to a failed insured bank, the insured deposit of all depositors shall be paid by the Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation within 90 days to all depositors the amount equal to the insured deposits.¹⁴ The Governor of the Central Bank when the need arises, he could add new conditions or vary the existing conditions to suit the exigency of the financial time in force.¹⁵ The Governor can do that with the approval of the Board of the Central Bank and it must be publish in a Gazette. The following situations may warrant the revocation of a license already granted to a bank:

⁹ 25 Billion Naira Recapitalization of Banks in Nigeria, www.academia.edu/Topic_25_Billion_Naira_Recapitalization_of_Banks_in_Nigeria>php. Visited on the 6th June, 2023; Central Bank of Nigeria: Reforms drive robust macroeconomic, www.oecdobserver.org/fullstory.php> visited on the 6th June, 2023; Monetary Policy Measures, https://www.cbn.gov.ng/Monetary_Policy_Measures> visited on the 6th June, 2023.

¹⁰ Section 3 (3) of BOFIA, 2020

¹¹ Section 3 (3) of the BOFIA, 2020.

¹² Section 4 of the BOFIA, 2020

¹³ *ibid*

¹⁴ Section 21 (1) (b) of the NDIC Act, 2006.

¹⁵ Section 5 of the BOFIA, 2020

- a. Where the bank ceases to carry on in Nigeria the type of banking business for which the bank was licensed for period 6 months or any period amounting in aggregate to 6 months;
- b. Went into liquidation or wound up or dissolved;
- c. Failure to meet the conditions of the grant;
- d. Insufficient fund to meet its liabilities;
- e. Failure to comply with any obligation imposed upon it under this Act or the Central Bank of Nigeria Act.¹⁶

It is pertinent to note that this power is given to the Central Bank of Nigeria to checkmate the operation of banks in Nigeria. The Central Bank of Nigeria is the sole authority that can either vary or revoke a license already granted to a bank that carried on the business of banking in Nigeria which must be in line with the requirements of the 2007 Act and must not derogate from it.¹⁷

iii. **Power to monitor and supervise operation of licensed banks in Nigeria:**

The 2007 Act, apart from investing the Central Bank with the powers to revoke license granted to any bank in Nigeria, it has the power to monitor and supervise the scope of operations of all banks in Nigeria which includes the internal operations of all banks for example, the opening and closing of all branches of banks within and outside Nigeria which must be done with the prior consent of the Bank,¹⁸ the operation of foreign banks in Nigeria which must be done with the prior consent of the Bank under the Act whether by Nigerian or non-Nigerian even the Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission Act cannot authorize such operations without being authorized by the Bank,¹⁹ any unauthorized operations is an offence punishable with fine of N1,000,000. The Bank is also authorized by the Act to monitor re-structuring, re-organizing, merger and disposal of interests in any bank in Nigeria whether for change of ownership and control, sale and disposal, transfer wholly or partly, amalgamation or

¹⁶ Section 12 of the BOFIA, 2020.

¹⁷ The essence of given the Central Bank of Nigeria the powers to grant, revoke and or vary the conditions stipulated in a licence is to control the financial and banking system in particular and the Nigerian economy in general. This will attract foreign investment thereby the legal framework has satisfied the need of having it in place from the very beginning

¹⁸ Section (6) of the BOFIA, 2020

¹⁹ *ibid*

merger with any person, reconstruction or above all to employ the management agent or to transfer its interests to such agent without the consent of the Bank and where such occurs, then any or all persons are liable of an offence punishable with N1,000,000.²⁰

iv. Power to approve the appointment of Auditors and their powers: The Bank shall approve the appointment of persons as auditors annually whose duty(s) is to report to the shareholders the annual balance sheet and profit and loss account of the bank which must be in line with the directives of the Central Bank from time to time.²¹ The person appointed as an approved auditor for that purpose must be someone who must be a member of one of the professional bodies recognized in Nigeria approved by the Central Bank, resident in Nigeria and carrying on business in Nigeria as a professional accountant or auditor.²²

v. The Power to examine specialized banks and other finance houses: The Central Bank of Nigeria has the power to examine the accounts and other books of specialized banks and other finance houses for periodic reports and findings for onward transmission to the President through the Minister. The specialized banks are:

- a. The Nigeria Industrial Development Bank;
- b. The Nigeria Agricultural and Co-operative Bank;
- c. The Nigeria Bank for Commerce and Industry;
- d. The Urban Development Bank;
- e. All Mortgage Institutions; f. Community Banks;
- g. The Peoples Bank;
- h. Bureau de Change,
- i. Discount houses and

²⁰ *ibid*

²¹ Section 29 (1) of the BOFIA, 2020.

²² Section 29 (2) of the BOFIA, 2020.

j. Other specialized banks and financial institutions as the Central Bank of Nigeria may specify from time to time.²³

It is instructive to note that the Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria can only conduct the examination, special examination, or investigation of the accounts, books, and affairs of the specialized banks and other finance houses in the interest of the public if the bank has been carrying on its business in a manner detrimental to the interest of depositors and creditors, or if the bank has insufficient assets to cover its liabilities to the public, or if the bank has been contravening the provisions of this Act.²⁴

vi. Power of supervision over banks, financial institutions and specialized banks: The Governor of the Central Bank has the power to appoint an officer of the Central Bank of Nigeria as Director of Banking Supervision who has the power to carry out supervisory duties in respect of banks, specialized banks and other financial institutions to examine in confidence the books and affairs of the banks, specialized banks and other financial institutions periodically; to access at all times books, accounts and vouchers of banks; to require information from directors, managers and officers for explanation as he deems necessary from time to time.²⁵

vii. Power over Failing Banks: The Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria in exercise of powers vested in him by Section 35 of this Act, upon being informed by the bank that it cannot meet its financial obligations under this Act; there is likelihood that the bank will suspend payment to any extent; it is insolvent, then the Governor may issue an order to prohibit the bank from extending any credit facility, require the bank take steps to do or not to do any action, remove any manager or officer of the bank in writing with effect from such date as may be set out in the order.²⁶ Where the affairs of the failing bank did not improve despite all steps taken as stipulated in section 35 of the Act, then the Central Bank may turn over the control and management of the failing bank to the Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation on such terms and conditions as the Central Bank may stipulate from time to time.²⁷ The management and control of the failing bank remains with the Corporation until when the Central

²³ Sections 30; 34 of the BOFIA, 2020.

²⁴ *ibid*

²⁵ *ibid*

²⁶ Section 35(2) of the BOFIA, 2020

²⁷ Section 36 of the BOFIA, 2020

Bank sees it necessary that the Corporation cannot remain in control of the business of the bank, then the Central Bank will invoke the provision of Section 39 of the Act to revoke the license of the bank of which the Corporation has assumed control over the bank.²⁸ Where the Central Bank revoked the license of the bank, the Corporation shall apply to the Federal High Court for the winding up order of the affairs of the bank.²⁹

4. DEFINITION OF CURRENCY REDESIGN

Currency is a form of exchange used to buy and sell goods and services. In essence, this currency, in the form of paper and cash, is normally issued by the government and is generally accepted as a form of payment at face value (i.e legal tender). In the modern world, money is the dominant medium of exchange, having long replaced barter as a means of trading goods and services. In the 21st century, new currencies have entered the vocabulary and exchange namely: Virtual currency, also known as crypto currencies such as Bitcoin, Ethereum and other virtual currencies have no physical form or government support in the United States³⁰. It is traded and stored electronically.

On the other hand, when you design a product and release it for use, there may be areas of the product that users will find most interesting. Again, there may be elements of your design that users don't like and that bring the user experience down. This may be because the consumer's needs are evolving rapidly and those products are slowly losing taste or being overexposed by competitors. Since the user experience is a highly sensitive product, it is your responsibility to fine-tune your core product to meet the needs of the customers and take their user experience to a better place. Now we can say it that it has been renewed. Updated changes will not only be made to make the product more attractive but high-quality changes will be made that improve the look of the product and provide a better user experience. You can't just wake up and decide to redesign. It should be driven by compelling reasons to improve your product. This

²⁸ Section 38 of the BOFIA, 2020

²⁹ Section 40 of the BOFIA, 2020.

³⁰ Fisher, Stanley "Financial System Soundness" Finance and Development, A Quarterly Publication of the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank, 1997.

process needs to be done carefully so you don't drag your stuff down thinking you're making a positive change.³¹

Currency redesign is a process undertaken by countries to update their banknotes and coins, often incorporating new security features, improved durability, and enhanced aesthetics.

5. HISTORY OF CURRENCY REDESIGN

The Nigerian currency Naira was introduced on January 1, 1963 as a result of the decision made by the Nigerian government. The Naira would serve as a rebirth from the imperial system inherited from the British Colonial administration. Through these years, Naira has evolved and so its redesign. In 1968, during the war, there was abuse of currency and trafficking as a result of the conflict and so the Naira was redesigned again. Obafemi Awolowo in 1973 supervised the creation of our indigenous currency.³² In April 1984, the colours of all the banknotes in circulation in Nigeria were changed with the exception of the 50 Kobo banknote to arrest the currency trafficking prevalent at the time. In 1991, the 50K and 1 naira were both coined. On 1st July, 1959 the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) issued Nigerian currency banknotes, while the WACB-issued banknotes and coins were withdrawn. It was not until 1st July, 1962 that the currency was changed to reflect the country's republican status. The notes were again changed in 1968 following the misuse of the currency banknotes during the civil war.³³

Sequel to the decision by the government to change from the metric to decimal, the name of the Nigerian currency was changed in January, 1973. The major unit of currency which used to be £1 ceased to exist and the one naira which was equivalent to ten shillings became the major unit, while the minor unit was called the kobo; hundreds of which made one naira.³⁴ On 11th February, 1977, a new banknote with the value of twenty naira (20) was issued. It was the highest denomination introduced at the time as a result of the growth of the economy; the preference for cash transactions and the need for convenience. The banknote was the first in Nigeria to bear the

³¹ Pillah, T. P. Currency Redesign and Monetary Policy of Nigeria: An Evaluation. *International International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research (IJPAMR)*, 2023. 8 (4), 46-53.

³² Central Bank of Nigeria (2015). History of Nigerian Currency. Accessed online from <https://www.cbn.gov.ng/currency/historycur.asp> on 5 June 2023

³³ Ibid

³⁴ Ibid

portrait of a prominent Nigerian citizen, the late Head of State, General Murtala Ramat Muhammed³⁵ who was the torch bearer of the Nigerian Revolution in July, 1975. The note was issued on the 1st anniversary of his assassination as a fitting tribute to a most illustrious son of Nigeria. He was declared a national hero on 1st October 1978.³⁶ On 2nd July, 1979, new currency banknotes of three denominations, namely 1, 5 and 10 were introduced. These notes were of the same size i.e., 151 X 78 mm as the 20 note issued on 11th February, 1977. In order to facilitate identification, distinctive colours were used for the various denominations.³⁷

In April 1984, the colours of all the banknotes in circulation were changed with the exception of the 50 Kobo banknote to arrest the currency trafficking prevalent at the time. In 1991, the 50K and 1 were both coined. In response to the expansion in economic activities and to facilitate an efficient payments system, the 100, 200, 500 and 1000 banknotes were introduced in December 1999, November 2000, April 2001 and October 2005 respectively.³⁸

On 28th February, 2007, as part of the economic reforms, 20 Naira was issued for the first time in polymer substrate, while the 50, 10 and 5 banknotes; as well as 1 and 50K coins were reissued in new designs, and the 2 Naira coin was introduced. On 30th September, 2009 the redesigned 50, 10 and 5 Naira banknotes were converted to polymer substrate following the successful performance of the 20 (polymer) banknotes. Thus, all lower denomination banknotes were now printed in the polymer substrate.³⁹

In a subsequent development, the Central Bank of Nigeria, as part of its contribution towards the celebration of the nation's 50th anniversary of Nigeria's Independence and 100 years of its existence as a nation, issued the 50 Commemorative polymer banknotes on 29th September, 2010; and the N100 Commemorative banknote on 19th December, 2014 respectively. The Central Bank of Nigeria Governor, Godwin

³⁵ The 4th Military head of state (1975-1976)

³⁶ *ibid*

³⁷ Business Day (2022). Naira redesign – the law and global best practices. Accessed online from https://businessday.ng/news/legal-business/article/naira-redesign-the-law-and-global_bestpractices/ on 5 June 2023

³⁸ *ibid*

³⁹ *ibid*

Emiefiele observed that over three trillion-naira notes are supposedly in circulation but merely a trillion have been accounted for by the banks.

Following this, in line with the provisions of section 2(b), section 18(a) and section 19(a) and (b) of the 1999 Nigerian constitution, the management of the Central Bank of Nigeria sought and obtained approval of President of the Nigeria, President Muhammadu Buhari (PMB) to redesign, produce, release and circulate new series of bank notes of N200, N500 and N1000 at all levels. Arrangements were finalized for the new currency to begin circulation on December 15, 2022 after been launched by PMB. The new and existing currencies remained legal tender and circulate together until January 31, 2023 when the existing currencies shall cease to be legal tender⁴⁰

Apart from the politicians who stockpiled the bigger nominations, the redesigning of N200, N500, and N1000 will help to address some of Nigeria's security threats especially laundering, kidnapping and terrorism. According to sources, the purpose of the policy is to mop up the huge amount of cash that is outside of the banking system, currently estimated to be 2.73 trillion or about 85% of the total cash in circulation. This move therefore rids the economy of a lot of 'black money' and will help to improve the health of the system, strengthen security and enable regulators to monitor the flow of funds in the country.⁴¹ Additionally, the monetary policy and currency design will help deepen financial inclusion by getting most people into the banking system. These sources believe this is a sine qua non to improving credit in the system and expanding productive activities, as well as usher in an improved cashless policy, and tighten the money supply which may combat inflation. While this may not be apparent to many Nigerians, only 4 out of the 54 African countries print their currencies in their countries, and Nigeria is one of them. Hence, a majority of African countries print their currencies abroad and import them the way we import other goods.⁴² Acknowledging that international best practice requires central banks and national authorities to issue new or redesigned currency notes every 5 to 8 years, the President of Nigeria noted that it is now almost 20 years since the last major redesign of the

⁴⁰ ibid

⁴¹ ibid

⁴² https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.thisdaylive.com/index.php/2022/11/08/naira_redesigneconomic-or-political-expediency/amp accessed on 04/06/2023

country's local currency was done. This implies that the Naira is long overdue to wear a new look.⁴³ This implies that a cycle of banknote redesign is generally aimed at achieving specific objectives, including but not limited to: improving security of banknotes, mitigating counterfeiting, preserving the collective national heritage, controlling currency in circulation, and reducing the overall cost of currency management.

6. IMPORTANCE AND RATIONALE FOR CURRENCY REDESIGN

According to the Central Bank of Nigeria, the redesigning of the naira banknotes is for the potential benefit of the economy as well as to improve on the level of security. The following are considered the relevance or importance of the redesigning of the naira currency:

i. **The Control of Money in Circulation and Promotion of E-naira**

The redesigning of the naira banknotes would mean people would have to put their old notes in the bank to enable them get the new notes. This in turn reduces the amount of money in circulation thereby reducing the rate of inflation. Since people would be forced to put their monies in the bank, it would encourage the cashless agenda complemented by a rise in use of the e-naira. According to Mr Godwin Emefiele, the Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria, over 85 percent of the naira in circulation was outside the banking system and this was affecting the monetary policies of the Central Bank of Nigeria which had to be put under control to ensure that the rate of inflation does not spike or rise uncontrollably.⁴⁴

ii. **The Mitigation of Counterfeit:** According to the Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria, Nigeria has failed to adopt the global practice of redesigning, producing and circulating their country's currency after every 5-8 years as the naira has not been redesigned for over 20 years. As a result of this, it has given room for counterfeiting of the naira currency. According to the Governor, the recent photographic technology and advancements in printing devices have made counterfeiting relatively easier. The activities of currency hoarders have become evident as very dirty, smelly Naira notes

⁴³ Central Bank of Nigeria (2022). Redesigning of the Currency. Accessed online from www.cbn.gov.ng. 04/06/2023

⁴⁴ *ibid*

have been in circulation, especially since political activities heightened across the country-an indication that such notes must have been hoarded in damp places and for a long period of time.⁴⁵

iii. **The reduction in the level of cash insecurity and money laundering**

According to the Central Bank of Nigeria, redesigning of the country's currency would reduce the level of cash insecurity as it would encourage and advance the cashless policy which is believed to thwart the activities of criminals like kidnappers who demands cash to set their victims free. At first, cash would not be available to pay the ransom thereby reducing the level of cash insecurity.⁴⁶ On the other hand, redesigning of the naira could be the government's ticket in reducing and even curbing money laundering in Nigeria. It is arguably true that some members of the public just move about with huge amounts of ill-gotten money they cannot invest or deposit into the banks because they are scared of getting caught by the authority.⁴⁷

The Central Bank of Nigeria highlights the following as reasons for the redesign of naira:

First reason is the control of the money supply. According to Isa,⁴⁸ the Central Bank of Nigeria will use the redesign of naira as a tool for controlling the supply of money in circulation. If the demand for naira rises, then its value will rise too reducing the high rate of inflation and price level of goods and services in Nigeria.⁴⁹ The redesign of naira would also mop up much liquidity in circulation used to fund terrorists and other crime related activities like kidnapping, banditry etc.

Second, it will reduce money hoarding. According to the Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria, Godwin Emefiele, 80 per cent of the naira currencies are outside the vaults of commercial banks. And with the redesigning of the currency, hoarding of banknotes by Nigerians, especially politicians and drug lords, will be reduced to the

⁴⁵ Vanguard (2022). 4 reasons CBN redesigned naira notes. Accessed online from <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2022/11/4-reasons-cbn-on-04/06/2023>

⁴⁶ Actionable Info, (2022). 10 Reasons Behind Naira Redesign. Accessed online from https://infomediang.com/naira_redesign/04/06/2023

⁴⁷ The Punch (2022). Redesign and redistribution of Nigerian currency. Accessed online from <https://punchng.com/redesign-and-redistribution-of-nigerian-currency/on-04/06/2023>

⁴⁸ Isa, A. (2022). Naira Redesign: Strategic Control of Multiple Challenges. Accessed online from <https://www.newtelegraphng.com/naira-redesign-strategic-control-of-multiple-challenges/#:~:text=%E2%80%9CThese%20challenges%20primarily%20include%2C%20significant,the%20CBN%20indicate%20that%20N2.>

⁴⁹ *ibid*

barest minimum.⁵⁰

Third, proper management and increase in the amount of naira in bank vaults. One important reason for the redesign of the naira is to ensure better and proper management of the currency and to increase the amount of naira in bank vaults. This will help reduce the amount of money in circulation and increase the amount of money in the commercial bank vaults. This could in turn encourage lending or lead to fall in interest rate as banks would increase their level of lending to the general public.⁵¹

Fourth, reduction of inflation rate in the economy; with the redesign of naira, the rate of inflation is expected to fall resulting from a decrease in the amount of money in circulation which would be inevitable since people would have to deposit their monies at the bank to get the new naira notes.⁵² With a fall in the amount of money in circulation, the price level of goods and services will eventually fall as a reaction to the low amount of money in supply. This in turn will reduce the rate of inflation. According to the Chairman of the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), Abdurashed Bawa, the redesign of naira notes would help in ensuring that hidden public funds are returned by fraudulent politicians thereby reducing the level of corruption and embezzlement of funds in Nigeria.⁵³

Fifth, the redesign of naira is long overdue. Following the global best practices, every country should redesign their currency every 5-8 years and the last time Nigeria redesigned her currency was over 20 years ago. This means Nigeria has to redesign her currency.⁵⁴

7. STATUTORY AUTHORITY ON CURRENCY REDESIGN IN NIGERIA

Essentially, the currency redesign and re-issue exercise comes under the broad powers of the bank to issue legal tender, re-issue and exchange currency notes and coins. In redesigning the currency and issuing the legal tender, it appears the Act envisages that the Central Bank of Nigeria should do so within the context of satisfying the other

⁵⁰ibid

⁵¹ Ejikonye, E. (2022). Naira Redesign: Economic or Political Expediency? Accessed online from https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.thisdaylive.com/index.php_04/06/2023_naira_redesigneconomic-or-political-expediency/amp/

⁵² Business Day (2022). Naira redesign – the law and global best practices. Accessed online from https://businessday.ng/news/legal-business/article/naira-redesign-the-law-and-global_bestpractices/ on 04/06/2023

⁵³ ibid

⁵⁴ ibid

monetary policy objectives to wit; ensuring monetary and price stability and promoting a sound financial system in Nigeria.⁵⁵

This has to do with the legal rights conferred on the Central Bank of Nigeria to redesign the national currency. Therefore, the community reading of Section 18(a), 18(b) and 20(3) of the CBN Act 2007 will portray a better justification to that effect. Be that as it may, Section 18 (a), and (b), establishes that: Central Bank of Nigeria shall

*“arrange for the printing of currency notes and the minting of coins; as well as issue, re-issue and exchange currency notes and coins at the Bank’s offices and at such agencies as it may, from time to time, establish or appoint”.*⁵⁶

Simply put, the Central Bank of Nigeria shall organize for printing of currency note, coins minting, and equally giving them out as and when due. Then, section 20 (3) of the same Act 4 establishes that:

*‘notwithstanding sub-sections (1) and (2) of this section, the Bank shall have power, if directed to do so by the President and after giving reasonable notice on that behalf, to call in any of its notes or coins on payment of the face value there and any note or coin with respect to which a notice has been given under this subsection, shall, on the expiration of the notice, cease to be legal tender.’*⁵⁷

Succinctly put, section 20(3), endorsed the Central Bank of Nigeria to redesign currency, if authorized by the president to embark on it, in line with his cogent notice on such. As seen in the foregoing, the only requirement for reissuing/redesign currency is that the Central Bank of Nigeria intends to do so, arranges for the processes, and gives reasonable notice of its intention to do so.

8. DECISION-MAKING PROCESS AND APPROVAL MECHANISMS

The redesign of the currency under the Central Bank of Nigeria Act 2007 is the responsibility of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). The CBN Act of 2007 (as

⁵⁵ Ibid

⁵⁶ CBN Act 2007

⁵⁷ CBN Act 2007

amended) vests in the Bank the responsibility to issue and manage the country's legal tender currency.⁵⁸

The following steps are taken in order to ensure efficiency in the decision-making process and approval of the currency redesign⁵⁹

1. **Proposal:** The process typically begins with a proposal to redesign the Naira currency. This proposal could originate from various sources, such as the Central Bank of Nigeria itself, the Nigerian government, or other stakeholders.
2. **Feasibility Study:** Once a proposal is made, the Central Bank of Nigeria will conduct a feasibility study to evaluate the necessity, cost, and impact of the proposed redesign. This study may consider factors like security features, durability, production costs, and public acceptance.
3. **Design Development:** If the feasibility study confirms the need for a redesign, the Central Bank of Nigeria will initiate the design development phase. This involves engaging artists, designers, and experts to create new currency designs that incorporate relevant elements of Nigerian culture, history, and security features.
4. **Stakeholder Consultation:** During the design development phase, the Central Bank of Nigeria may engage in consultations with various stakeholders, including government officials, financial institutions, security agencies, and the general public. These consultations help gather feedback, address concerns, and ensure the new currency design aligns with the country's values and aspirations.
5. **Approval Process:** Once the design is finalized, it goes through an approval process within the Central Bank of Nigeria and possibly other government entities. The specific approval mechanisms may vary, but they typically involve review by relevant committees, senior management, and ultimately, the Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria.
6. **Printing and Distribution:** After receiving the necessary approvals, the Central Bank of Nigeria will initiate the printing of the redesigned Naira notes in collaboration with

⁵⁸ Section 18 CBN Act 2007

⁵⁹ Akintunde Jide and Hile Martins, 'Institutions, Policies and Development: CBN Act 2007 is Contemporary Good Law,' *Financial Nigeria Magazine*, July 2012. Also at http://www.financialnigeria.com/development/developmentreport_category_item_detail.aspx?categoryid=5&item=248

authorized printing firms. The new currency will then be distributed through the banking system to replace the existing currency in circulation gradually.

It's important to note that the CBN Act 2007 and other relevant guidelines provide the legal framework and authority for the CBN to make decisions regarding currency design and issuance. The specific details of the decision-making process and approval mechanisms may be outlined in internal policies and guidelines established by the Central Bank of Nigeria.⁶⁰

9. COLLABORATION WITH RELEVANT STAKEHOLDERS

The CBN is responsible for currency management and redesign in Nigeria. When it comes to currency redesign, collaboration with relevant stakeholders is essential. The CBN collaborated with relevant stakeholders in the redesign of the currency. The stakeholders involved in the currency redesign include:

1. **Government Agencies:** The CBN would likely collaborate with various government agencies to ensure that the currency redesign aligns with the broader economic and financial policies of the government. This may involve consultations with entities such as the Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Budget and National Planning, and other relevant government bodies.
2. **Financial Institutions:** Collaboration with banks and other financial institutions is crucial during currency redesign. The CBN may consult with these stakeholders to gather input on design features, security features, and other aspects that impact the banking industry. Feedback from financial institutions can help ensure a smooth transition and compatibility with existing systems.
3. **Security Agencies:** The CBN would likely work closely with security agencies, such as law enforcement agencies and intelligence services, to enhance the security features of the redesigned currency. Collaboration with these stakeholders can help in the identification and prevention of counterfeiting activities, which is a critical concern during currency redesign.

⁶⁰ Familoni, J.A., *Monetary and Fiscal Policy: Concepts and Practice*, Concepts and Practice, Ado-Ekiti, FemFem, Publishing, 2001.

4. Cash Management Companies: Collaborating with cash management companies, which are responsible for the distribution and circulation of cash, is essential. The CBN may seek their input on issues related to handling, logistics, and efficient distribution of the redesigned currency to ensure a seamless transition.

5. Retailers and Merchants: Engaging with retailers and merchants is important to understand their requirements and ensure that the redesigned currency is easily accepted and integrated into the retail sector. Collaboration with these stakeholders can help identify any potential challenges or adjustments needed in cash handling and point-of-sale systems.

6. Public Awareness and Education: The CBN may collaborate with media organizations, educational institutions, and other stakeholders to create awareness campaigns and educate the general public about the currency redesign. This collaboration can help ensure a smooth transition and minimize confusion or misconceptions among the public.

10. AUTHORITY TO DETERMINE CURRENCY DENOMINATION

The authority to determine currency denominations in Nigeria rests with the CBN.⁶¹ The CBN Act empowers the CBN to issue and regulate the country's currency.

Section 2 (b) of the CBN Act (2007) states that one of the principal objectives of the Central Bank of Nigeria is to ensure monetary and price stability. This includes the power to determine the denominations of the legal tender issued by the CBN. The Act grants the CBN the authority to prescribe the forms and denominations of Nigeria's currency, including banknotes and coins.

The CBN, as the central monetary authority in Nigeria, is responsible for managing the country's currency supply, ensuring its stability, and promoting its efficient circulation. As part of this role, the CBN has the power to introduce new currency denominations, withdraw existing denominations, and make changes to the design or security features of banknotes and coins.

11. AUTHORITY TO IMPLEMENT SECURITY FEATURES

⁶¹ *ibid*

The CBN has the authority to implement security features on the Nigerian currency, the Naira. The CBN Act grants the bank a wide range of powers and functions related to currency management and monetary policy in Nigeria.⁶²

Specifically, Section 2(d) of the CBN Act empowers the CBN to issue and manage legal tender currency in Nigeria. This includes the responsibility to design, produce, and distribute banknotes and coins. As part of this responsibility, the CBN has the authority to incorporate various security features on the currency to deter counterfeiting and ensure its integrity.⁶³

The CBN Act also grants the CBN the authority to regulate and supervise banking and financial institutions in Nigeria, including measures to safeguard the stability and security of the financial system. This broader mandate can indirectly contribute to the implementation of security features on the Naira, as it helps to maintain public confidence in the currency and the overall financial system.

12. GUIDELINES FOR CURRENCY DESIGN AND REDESIGN.

The CBN Act 2007 provides the legal framework for currency design and redesign in Nigeria. While the specific guidelines may vary over time, here are some general considerations for currency design and redesign under the CBN Act:

1. **Security Features:** Currency design should incorporate robust security features to prevent counterfeiting. These features may include watermarks, security threads, micro printing, holograms, and other advanced technologies.
2. **Cultural Representation:** Currency should reflect the cultural diversity and heritage of Nigeria. It may include images, symbols, or motifs that represent the country's history, traditions, landmarks, or achievements.
3. **Accessibility and Inclusivity:** Currency should be designed with consideration for individuals with visual impairments or other disabilities. Features like tactile marks or varying sizes can help people identify different denominations by touch.

⁶² Ibid

⁶³ ibid

4. **Durability and Longevity:** Currency should be designed to withstand the rigors of circulation and have a reasonable lifespan. Durable materials and printing techniques are crucial to ensure the longevity of banknotes.
5. **Aesthetic Appeal:** Currency design should strive for aesthetic appeal while maintaining a distinct Nigerian identity. The overall design, color scheme, and typography should be visually appealing and recognizable.
6. **Currency Denominations:** The CBN determines the denominations of currency based on the country's economic needs, usage patterns, and inflation rates. The design and redesign process may consider the introduction or elimination of certain denominations if necessary.
7. **Technical Specifications:** Currency design should adhere to specific technical specifications related to size, weight, composition, and printing methods. These specifications are crucial for maintaining compatibility with vending machines, ATMs, and other cash handling equipment.
8. **Legal Authority:** The CBN has the sole authority to issue and regulate the Nigerian currency. The design and redesign of currency must comply with the regulations and guidelines set forth by the CBN Act 2007.

13. IMPLEMENTATION OF CURRENCY POLICY GUIDELINES.

The CBN implements its currency policy guidelines through various measures and mechanisms.⁶⁴ Here are some of the key methods used by the CBN:

1. **Monetary Policy:** The CBN formulates and implements monetary policies to regulate the money supply in the economy. It uses tools such as open market operations, reserve requirements, and discount rates to manage liquidity, control inflation, and stabilize the value of the currency.
2. **Exchange Rate Management:** The Central Bank of Nigeria intervenes in the foreign exchange market to manage the exchange rate of the Nigerian Naira. It may conduct periodic auctions, provide foreign exchange to authorized dealers, or implement direct interventions to influence the supply and demand dynamics of the currency.

⁶⁴ *ibid*

3. Cash Reserve Ratio (CRR): The Central Bank of Nigeria sets a minimum percentage of total customer deposits that banks must maintain as reserves. By adjusting the CRR, the Central Bank of Nigeria regulates the liquidity levels in the banking system and controls the lending capacity of commercial banks.

4. Statutory Cash Ratio (SCR): The Central Bank of Nigeria also sets a statutory cash ratio for primary mortgage banks, microfinance banks, and other specialized institutions. Similar to the CRR, this ratio determines the minimum reserve requirement for these institutions.

5. Direct Credit Controls: In some cases, the Central Bank of Nigeria may impose direct credit controls to influence lending patterns and channel credit towards specific sectors deemed important for the economy's development. This can involve sector-specific loan limits, interest rate caps, or credit allocation requirements.

6. Foreign Exchange Restrictions: The Central Bank of Nigeria may implement restrictions on access to foreign exchange for certain transactions or goods. This could involve imposing import or export controls, limiting access to foreign exchange for specific purposes, or introducing targeted exchange rate windows for certain sectors.

7. Financial Sector Supervision: The CBN oversees and regulates the banking and financial sector to ensure compliance with currency policy guidelines. It conducts regular inspections, issues guidelines, and enforces prudential regulations to maintain stability and integrity within the financial system.

These measures collectively enable the Central Bank of Nigeria to implement its currency policy guidelines and achieve its objectives of price stability, exchange rate management, and overall economic development in Nigeria. It's worth noting that specific policies and guidelines may change over time as per the Central Bank of Nigeria's assessment of economic conditions and priorities.⁶⁵

14. COMPLIANCE AND ENFORCEMENT MEASURES

⁶⁵ *ibid*

In general, compliance and enforcement measures are put in place to ensure that guidelines related to currency redesign are followed effectively. These measures may include:

1. **Legislation and Regulations:** Governments often pass laws and regulations to establish the legal framework for currency redesign. These laws define the guidelines, procedures, and standards that need to be followed. They also outline the consequences for non-compliance.
2. **Central Bank Oversight:** The CBN in the case of Nigeria is responsible for implementing and enforcing currency redesign guidelines. The central bank may establish specific departments or units dedicated to overseeing the compliance and enforcement aspects of currency redesign.
3. **Compliance Audits:** Regular audits may be conducted to assess compliance with currency redesign guidelines. These audits can be carried out by internal or external auditors who evaluate whether the redesign process adheres to the established guidelines and meets the required standards.
4. **Monitoring and Reporting:** The central bank may closely monitor the currency redesign process to ensure compliance. This can involve reviewing progress reports, inspecting production facilities, and verifying the quality and security features of the new currency.
5. **Penalties and Sanctions:** Non-compliance with currency redesign guidelines may result in penalties or sanctions. These can vary depending on the severity of the violation and may include fines, legal action, or even criminal charges in cases of counterfeiting or fraudulent activities.⁶⁶
6. **Public Education and Awareness:** The central bank may undertake public awareness campaigns to educate the general population, financial institutions, and other stakeholders about the currency redesign guidelines. This helps to create a sense of compliance and encourages the public to report any suspicious activities related to the currency.

⁶⁶ *ibid*

15. REPORTING AND ACCOUNTABILITY REQUIREMENTS

When it comes to currency redesign guidelines, reporting and accountability requirements play a crucial role in ensuring transparency, security, and adherence to established protocols. Here are some common reporting and accountability elements:

1. **Documentation:** Currency redesign guidelines often mandate the creation of comprehensive documentation that outlines the design process, decision-making criteria, and relevant specifications. This documentation serves as a reference for internal teams, external stakeholders, and auditors.
2. **Reporting on Design Changes:** Any changes made to currency design, including modifications to security features, denominations, or visual elements, should be documented and reported. These reports may include justifications for the changes, technical details, and impact assessments.
3. **Security Measures:** Currency redesign guidelines typically include strict security requirements. Reports on security measures taken during the redesign process, such as anti-counterfeiting technologies, should be documented and periodically reviewed to ensure compliance with standards.
4. **Financial Accountability:** Currency redesign often involves significant financial considerations, including production costs, distribution expenses, and impact on existing currency stocks. Reporting on financial aspects, including budget allocations, cost-benefit analyses, and accounting for expenditures, helps ensure transparency and accountability.
5. **Stakeholder Engagement:** Guidelines may emphasize the importance of engaging relevant stakeholders throughout the redesign process. Reporting on stakeholder consultations, feedback received, and how their concerns were addressed demonstrates inclusivity and accountability.
6. **Compliance with Legal and Regulatory Frameworks:** Currency redesign must comply with applicable laws and regulations. Reporting on the compliance efforts, including legal reviews, regulatory assessments, and certifications obtained, helps demonstrate adherence to legal requirements.

7. Independent Audits: Independent audits of the currency redesign process can provide an objective assessment of compliance, effectiveness, and adherence to established guidelines. Audit reports should highlight any findings, recommendations, or areas for improvement.

8. Public Disclosure: To promote transparency and public trust, guidelines may require the public disclosure of relevant information related to the currency redesign. This may include sharing design concepts, security features, and relevant updates through official channels.

9. Ongoing Monitoring and Evaluation: Reporting and accountability requirements often extend beyond the redesign phase. Regular monitoring and evaluation of the currency's performance, durability, security, and public acceptance should be conducted, and reports should be generated to track progress and inform future decision-making.

Over the years, Nigeria has experienced the introduction and redesigning of her currencies in circulations with the Central Bank of Nigeria playing pivoted roles in protecting its stability. This sector's operation and performance have a direct impact on achieving macroeconomic goals while also improving the economy, recently the Central Bank of Nigeria issued a statement that it has concluded plans to redesign the Naira. The Central Bank of Nigeria Governor cited money hoarding, inflation, and counterfeiting as major reasons for its unusual decision. The Central Bank of Nigeria claims that about N2.73 trillion of the N3.23 trillion currency in circulation in Nigeria, is outside the bank vaults. This is about 85% of the total money in circulation. Also, the Naira is not as secured as it ought to be, as it is easier to counterfeit the N500 and N1000 denominations.⁶⁷

This policy has elicited serious debate amongst Economists, Lawyers, and other policy experts. Many of them hold the view that this policy change holds no significant economic benefits for the people and is a distraction in the midst of serious ravaging economic issues, The Central Bank of Nigeria in its most recent report, 2020 Currency Report, states that a total of 67,265 pieces of counterfeit notes with a nominal value of

⁶⁷ <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/115634/> MPRA Paper No. 115634, posted 13 Dec 2022 08:10 UTC Accessed on 23rd September 2023

N56.83 million was confiscated in 2020, indicating a 20.80% decrease in volume and 12.18% decrease in value, compared with 84,934 pieces valued at N64.71 million in 2019.⁶⁸ The Global standard for number of counterfeits per million, is 100. The ratio of counterfeit notes to volume of banknotes in circulation was 13 pieces per million in 2020, compared to 20 pieces per million banknotes in 2019. In line with the research objective, this chapter examines how the Central Bank of Nigeria exercises its powers and extent of compliance with the Central Bank of Nigeria Act 2007 by the Central Bank in 2023 policy and controversy surrounding the currency redesign in 2023.

16.CBN CURRENCY REDESIGN IN 2023

The Central Bank of Nigeria currency redesign was a policy announced by the Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Mr Godwin Emefiele on 26 October 2022.⁶⁹ The policy aimed to redesign the highest denominations of the Naira, the Nigerian currency (N200, N500 and N1000 notes) by introducing new security features and changing their colors.⁷⁰

The policy also set a deadline of 31 January 2023 for all old notes to be deposited in banks in exchange for new ones.⁷¹ The Central Bank of Nigeria said that the old notes would stop being legal tender after that date and would become useless.⁷²

The Central Bank of Nigeria gave some reasons for the currency redesign, such as to curb inflation, reduce corruption, enhance security, and improve the aesthetics of the naira. The Central Bank of Nigeria also said that the policy would help to track illicit financial flows and money laundering activities.

However, the policy faced a lot of criticism and opposition from various stakeholders, such as the public, the banks, the politicians, and the judiciary.⁷³ Some of the challenges and criticisms that arose from the policy were that the timing of the policy was seen as politically motivated, as it coincided with the 2023 general election in

⁶⁸ *ibid*

⁶⁹ TechCabal. <https://techcabal.com/2023/03/03/supreme-court-extends-currency-deadline/>. Accessed on 23rd September 2023

⁷⁰ *ibid*

⁷¹ *ibid*

⁷² At 2.66tn, Currency in Circulation Hits Record High in 2023. <https://www.thisdaylive.com/index.php/2023/09/18/at-2-66tn-currency-in-circulation-hits-record-high-in-2023>. Accessed on 23rd September 2023

⁷³ *ibid*

Nigeria. Some critics argued that the policy was an attempt to disrupt the electoral process and disenfranchise voters by making it difficult for them to access cash.

The policy also caused a lot of inconvenience and hardship for the public, especially those in rural areas, who had limited access to banking services and facilities. Many people had to travel long distances and queue for hours to exchange their old notes for new ones.

Furthermore, the policy created a shortage of cash in circulation, as many people hoarded the new notes and did not deposit them in banks. This led to a spike in inflation, as prices of goods and services increased due to scarcity of money.

The policy also faced legal challenges, as some groups filed lawsuits against the Central Bank of Nigeria and sought injunctions to stop the implementation of the policy. On 3 March 2023, the Supreme Court ruled that all the old notes would remain legal tender until 31 December 2023, nullifying the CBN's deadline.⁷⁴

The policy also had security implications, as some criminals took advantage of the confusion and chaos caused by the policy to rob and defraud unsuspecting people. Some fake notes also circulated in the market, as some fraudsters printed counterfeit versions of the new notes.⁷⁵

17. EXTENT OF COMPLIANCE BY CBN IN 2023 POLICY

The CBN Act 2007 is the legal framework that governs the operations and functions of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). The Act defines the objectives, powers, duties, and responsibilities of the CBN, as well as the structure and management of the Bank. The Act also provides for the establishment of the Monetary Policy Committee, the Financial Services Regulation Co-ordinating Committee, and the Currency Conversion Fund. The Act also regulates the issuance, circulation, and management of the Nigerian currency, the Naira.⁷⁶

⁷⁴ Supreme Court rules that old notes remain legal tender - TechCabal. <https://techcabal.com/2023/03/03/supreme-court-extends-currency-deadline/>. Accessed on 23rd September 2023

⁷⁵ Currency in Circulation Surpasses N2 Trillion as New CBN Governor <https://www.legit.ng/business-economy/economy/1555278-currency-circulation-surpasses-n2-trillion-cbn-governor-assumes-duty/>. Accessed on 23rd September 2023

⁷⁶ *ibid*

The Central Bank of Nigeria's naira redesign policy in 2023 is a controversial and unprecedented move by the apex bank to replace the old naira notes of N200, N500, and N1000 with new ones by January 31, 2023. The Central Bank of Nigeria claims that the policy is aimed at curbing corruption, inflation, currency fraud, and kidnapping for ransom, as well as enhancing the cashless economy and digital payment systems. However, the policy has faced strong opposition and criticism from various stakeholders, including the federal government, state governments, civil society groups, political parties, and ordinary Nigerians. The policy has also been challenged in court by some states that argue that it violates their constitutional rights and interests.⁷⁷

The extent of compliance with the Central Bank of Nigeria Act 2007 by the Central Bank of Nigeria in implementing the naira redesign policy in 2023 is a matter of debate and interpretation. On one hand, some have argued that the Central Bank of Nigeria has acted within its mandate and powers as conferred by the Act, especially in relation to its functions of issuing and managing the national currency, maintaining price stability, promoting a sound financial system, and fostering economic development. On the other hand, some have contended that the Central Bank of Nigeria has overstepped its bounds and violated some provisions of the Act, such as those relating to consultation with relevant authorities, transparency and accountability, protection of public interest, and respect for due process and rule of law. Some legal experts have argued that the policy may violate some provisions of the CBN Act of 2007, such as Section 20(4), which states that

"The Bank shall arrange for the exchange at par at its offices and agencies throughout Nigeria of any notes or coins issued by it which have been withdrawn from circulation".

They have also questioned whether the policy is consistent with Section 2(b) of the CBN Act of 2007, which states that one of the objects of the Bank is

"to maintain external reserves to safeguard the international value of the legal tender currency".

⁷⁷ ibid

Therefore, there is no a definitive answer to this question, as different perspectives may have different opinions on the legality and legitimacy of the CBN's naira redesign policy in 2023. However, one thing that is clear is that the policy has generated a lot of controversy and uncertainty in the country's political and economic landscape. The policy has also raised important questions about the role and independence of the Central Bank of Nigeria as Nigeria's central bank and monetary authority. This research concluded that the Central Bank of Nigeria complied with some of the provisions of the Central Bank of Nigeria Act and disregards some of the most important aspect of the processes like consultation with relevant authorities, transparency and accountability, protection of public interest, and respect for due process and rule of law

18. CONTROVERSY SURROUNDING THE CURRENCY REDESIGN IN 2023

The currency redesign in 2023 was a controversial policy that aimed to replace the old N200, N500 and N1000 notes with new ones. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) claimed that the policy would help to curb corruption, counterfeiting, kidnapping, terrorism and inflation, as well as promote a cashless economy.⁷⁸ However, the policy faced strong opposition from various stakeholders, including the finance minister, state governors, legislators, judges, business owners and ordinary citizens.⁷⁹ Some of the criticisms and challenges that the policy encountered were:

- i. The policy was implemented without proper consultation and communication with the public and other relevant authorities.
- ii. The policy was rushed and poorly timed, as it coincided with the general election period when cash politics was prevalent
- iii. The policy caused severe shortages of the new banknotes, leading to long queues at banks, ATMs and other cash points.

⁷⁸ Currency Redesign | Engraving & Printing. <https://www.bep.gov/currency/currency-redesign>. Accessed on 23rd September 2023

⁷⁹ Nigeria's currency redesign 2023: A case study approach, By Tope Fasua. <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/opinion/580328-nigerias-currency-redesign-2023-a-case-study-approach-by-tope-fasua.html>. Accessed on 23rd September 2023

- iv. The policy disrupted economic activities, especially in the informal sector that relied heavily on cash transactions.
- v. The policy violated the principle of cost-benefit analysis, as the benefits of the policy were unclear and uncertain, while the costs were enormous and evident.
- vi. The policy was declared illegal and invalids by the Supreme Court, which ruled that the presidential directive to discontinue the use of old naira notes was unconstitutional.⁸⁰

The currency redesign in 2023 was a failed attempt to reform the Nigerian monetary system that resulted in social unrest, economic hardship and political instability. It was widely regarded as one of the worst policies in Nigeria's history.

19. CONCLUSION

The CBN act of 2007 gives the Central Bank of Nigeria the authority to redesign and reissue the national currency, subject to the approval of the President. The Central Bank of Nigeria acted within its mandate and powers as conferred by the Act, especially in relation to its functions of issuing and managing the national currency, maintaining price stability, promoting a sound financial system, and fostering economic development. However, the recent policy was implemented without adequate consultation or communication with the relevant authorities and the public. The policy was rushed and poorly timed, as it coincided with the preparations for the 2023 general elections. The policy was unnecessary and ineffective, as it did not address the root causes of the economic and security challenges facing Nigeria. It also stirred negative consequences such as increment in transaction costs, creating liquidity shortages, encouraging black market activities, and triggering social unrest.

The findings reveal that the currency redesign process in Nigeria is only governed by the legal and regulatory frameworks established by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Act 2007. The Central Bank of Nigeria has the sole right and authority to issue legal tender currency notes and coins in Nigeria. The Central Bank of Nigeria also has the power to determine the exchange rate of the naira, maintain external reserves, and promote monetary stability and a sound financial system. The Central Bank of Nigeria

⁸⁰ *ibid*

exercises these powers in practice by engaging in currency issue and distribution, foreign exchange management, debt management, and monetary policy functions. The Central Bank of Nigeria also has the power to call in, withdraw, or demonetize any of its notes or coins on the direction of the President and after giving reasonable notice.

The findings further reveal that the president's consent as one of the criteria for currency redesign may have a potential impact on the economy. This is because the policy can be politicized at the expense of the nation as a whole.

How the issue of specific powers granted to the CBN concerning currency redesign, the findings reveal that the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) is the sole authority responsible for the printing, redesigning, destroying, and distributing of the Nigerian currency, the naira, according to the CBN Act of 2007. The CBN Act of 2007 does not explicitly state the conditions or procedures for redesigning or replacing the existing currency notes and coins. However, it gives the Central Bank of Nigeria the authority to make regulations for the effective discharge of its functions. Therefore, the Central Bank of Nigeria can decide to redesign or replace the currency notes and coins based on its own discretion and judgment, as long as it is in line with its objectives and duties. The policy implications of currency redesign in Nigeria are diverse and intricate, affecting various aspects of the economy, such as inflation, exchange rate, fiscal policy, financial inclusion, and national identity. The policy challenges of currency redesign in Nigeria include the high cost of production and logistics, the public perception and acceptance and the coordination with other stakeholders. Therefore, it is the research findings that the specific provisions that empower the Central Bank of Nigeria regarding currency redesign are not elaborate.

Regarding how the Central Bank of Nigeria exercises these powers in practice, particularly in the process of currency issuance, withdrawal, and demonetization? The finding reveals that the Central Bank of Nigeria is responsible for issuing and distributing legal tender currency notes and coins within the economy, as well as maintaining the external reserves of the country. The Central Bank of Nigeria has introduced several currency reforms since 1959, when it replaced the West African Currency Board (WACB) pound with the Nigerian pound.

The findings further reveal that the 2023 currency redesign policy was unnecessary and ineffective, as it did not address the root causes of the economic and security

challenges facing Nigeria. It has also stirred negative consequences such as increased transaction cost, created liquidity shortages, encouraged black market activities, and triggered social unrest.

Furthermore, the findings reveal that the eNaira policy was premature as it failed to bring the multiple benefits, such as increasing financial inclusion, facilitating remittances, enhancing the payments system, and reducing the cost of currency production and management. However, the eNaira also faces potential risks and challenges, such as cyberattacks, privacy issues, regulatory gaps, and public acceptance.

The research, while stressing that the CBN has the power to redesign the Nigerian currency, has revealed that the policy is a complex and controversial one that involves legal, economic, political, ethical, and social dimensions. The policy has both advantages and disadvantages for Nigeria and its people. The policy also reflects the challenges and opportunities that Nigeria faces as a developing country in a globalised world. The policy may have significant implications for Nigeria's future development and stability. Therefore, it is important that Nigerians are well-informed about the policy and its impacts, and that they engage in constructive dialogue and debate on how to make it work for their best interests.

20. RECOMMENDATION

Redesigning the naira is a good monetary policy, which is proxied by the interest rate and the exchange rate, to prevent naira counterfeiting and control the amount of currency in circulation to reduce inflation. This research has examined the powers of the Central Bank of Nigeria on currency redesign under the CBN Act 2007. Based on the research, the following recommendations have been made:

1. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) should ensure that the legal and regulatory frameworks governing the currency redesign process in Nigeria are clear, consistent, and transparent. The Central Bank of Nigeria has the power to redesign and re-distribute currencies under sections 2, 18 and 20 of the CBN Act, 2007.⁸¹ However, the CBN should also consult and collaborate with other relevant stakeholders, such as the Federal Government, the National Assembly,

⁸¹ *ibid*

the Deposit Money Banks (DMBs), and the public, to ensure a smooth and successful implementation of the currency redesign policy.

2. The Central Bank of Nigeria should exercise its specific powers concerning currency redesign in a prudent and responsible manner, taking into account the economic and social impacts of its decisions. The Central Bank of Nigeria should balance its objectives of curbing illicit financial flows, enhancing security features, and promoting a cashless economy, with the potential costs and risks of currency redesign, such as inflation, liquidity crunch, public inconvenience, and loss of confidence. The Central Bank of Nigeria should also conduct adequate research, development, and trials on the new generation bank notes before issuing them to the public, as was done by the Reserve Bank of Australia in 1988.⁸²
3. The Central Bank of Nigeria should adopt a phased and gradual approach in the process of currency issuance, withdrawal, and demonetization. The Central Bank of Nigeria should ensure that there is sufficient supply of the new notes and coins in circulation, while allowing enough time for the public to exchange or deposit the old notes.
4. The legislature should review and amend the CBN Act of 2007 to clarify and strengthen the mandate and autonomy of the Central Bank of Nigeria in relation to the design and issuance of the naira.
5. The Central Bank of Nigeria should ensure that its policy decisions are based on sound economic principles and evidence, and that they are consistent with its objectives of maintaining price stability, supporting economic growth, and ensuring financial system stability.
6. The Central Bank of Nigeria should conduct a thorough cost-benefit analysis of the naira redesign policy, taking into account the potential impacts on various aspects of the economy, such as inflation, exchange rate, cash demand, financial inclusion, security, and governance. The Central Bank of Nigeria should also

⁸²) Naira redesign – the law and global best practices. <https://businessday.ng/news/legal-business/article/naira-redesign-the-law-and-global-best-practices/>. Accessed 12/10/2023

consider alternative measures to achieve its desired goals, such as enhancing the security features of the existing notes, promoting digital payments, and strengthening anti-money laundering and counter-terrorism financing regulations.

7. The Central Bank of Nigeria should engage in extensive consultation and communication with all relevant stakeholders, such as the federal and state governments, the National Assembly, the judiciary, the banking sector, the business community, the civil society, and the general public. The Central Bank of Nigeria should explain the rationale, objectives, benefits, costs, and risks of the naira redesign policy, and solicit feedback and suggestions from various perspectives. The Central Bank of Nigeria should also address any concerns or misconceptions that may arise from the policy announcement.